

CHANGING MINDSET FOR DIGITAL LEARNING IN ACADEMIC LIBRARY: A THEORETICAL GLIMPING

R. Sebastiyani* & V. Ramesh Babu**

* Research Scholar & Librarian, Bharathidasan University, Trichy, Tamilnadu

** Librarian & Head, TBML College, Porayar, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: R. Sebastiyani & V. Ramesh Babu, "Changing Mindset for Digital Learning in Academic Library: A Theoretical Glimpsing", *International Journal of Computational Research and Development*, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 66-69, 2017.

Abstract:

This attempt is to find the problem in digital screen reading habit in academic libraries for changing the user attitude rather than printed culture. A digital capability is making cross functional proficiency in the way of process, practices and user relationships enabled by digital media and infrastructure. This review evaluates on literature from different field of ICT, social and neuro scientific impacts that the internet is having on the practice of reading. A compact general view is presented of the recent transformation of academic libraries into a mainstay of online digital text in addition to printed books and other materials benefited by all graduates in academic libraries.

Key Words: Mindset, Digital Learning, Academic Library, ICT, Information, User/Reader & Institution

1. Introduction:

Akin to every revolution, the digital revolution in the 20th century and the 21st century ushers incredible impact on society. Socio-political and cultural changes have emerged and effected every stratum of the global community. The technology of digital learning culture is becoming an inevitable one in our daily lives. The new technology is changing the way of people can learn and interact with each other. Digital screen reading habit is vital role to change the user attitude rather than printed culture. Internet – Intranet and its medium of digital text accessed offline, as well as online sources, can be utilized in a digital projector like a computer, laptop, iPad and smart cell phone at anywhere in some time so that distance is no barrier in this learning of academic library atmosphere.

University skill @ the UK (2009) suggested that DL encompasses a huge variety of activities which could take place almost anywhere, people feel that this kind of technology DL is the best way to easy to recollect sweet memories for examination purposes and other usages keeping active. (Offorma-2002) DL is an institutional medium that permits alternative approaches to curriculum implementation in an ICT age. Independents (2000) According to Robin Ann martin, alternative educational cultures are learner centered, progressive, holistic to create and find alternative educational system learning. Popular technology writer Nicholas Carr recently suggested that we are at a turning point in the history of modern literate society as books and book reading is in their "cultural twilight." Robert Darnton, the historian, and Director of the Harvard University Library have stated that readers today feel the ground shifting beneath their feet, tipping toward a new era that will be determined by innovations in academic libraries.

In this process of DL segment, the economic strategy is involved in making connections with digital resources and users in an educational institution has to take in considering and implementing users their requirements effectively. The market effect of DL alters the nature of the competition can be achieved through gains the customer through increased awareness and transparency of information, especially for price information in business motivation for goods and services.

2. Objective of this Study:

- ✓ To reduce the time and cost in using the digital contents.
- ✓ To strengthen the user knowledge through ICT.

3. Special Character of Digital Learning:

- ✓ Rapid rectification of documents.
- ✓ Empower achievement of goals within a minute.
- ✓ Easy to adopt the new applications in convenient path.
- ✓ Orientation towards innovations, improvements and overcoming constraints.
- ✓ Strong collaboration with others easily.
- ✓ Faster progression in unpredictable career.
- ✓ Focus on documents only.
- ✓ Flat hierarchy.

4. Reading Attitude on Online Searching:

4.1 Short Time Learning: There is a relationship between the low level of information literacy skill and academic performance low performing students typically have low information literacy skill from under graduates suggested by Hargittai-2002, Currie., et al-2010, De Rosa, et al-2006, Nicholas, et al-2009, and Weiler-2005.

4.2 Long Time Learning: This is most meaning full learning and it is very much required for complication activities which are received of oral observation from first year undergraduates to professors are exhibiting a similar tendency to search “horizontally” instead of “vertically,” skimming information and bouncing quickly from place to place.

4.3 Minute Time Learning: Their users “power browser” horizontally through titles, contents and extract abstracts going for quick wins (Nielsen-2008 and Weinreich, et al-2008). Web site users tend to browse pages rapidly and read only about 20 percent of the text on an average page.

5. Statement of Problem:

As part of digital learning, “Digital India” which is initiated by Shri Narendra Moodi on July-1-2015 for the purpose of the citizen can access the digital literacy in electronically at economically for getting placement in our country. This study came to analysis about the digital India observation that there are two major concepts has been identified and some oral feedback has been observed from people in the slums and remote places of the villages in our county have little opportunity to utilize the printer sources rather than digital sources by only affluent class benefiting group.

On the other hand, today, many readers coming to the library is falling down due to lack of interest, methodology teaching, amorphous readymade sources, place of atmosphere, etc. Therefore an urgent requires replacing and modifying the hard sources into digital format through the internet as well as intranet with an advanced development of ICT to provide suitable solutions. In addition to that, the effective training is very much required for students to utilize an effective in a proper manner.

Besides, there are many reasons to habituate in retrieving the opting information to the right user requirement; here some suitable reasons are pointed out as follows,

- ✓ All Academic libraries could not pay full satisfaction to their users, due to insufficient fund in acquiring the printed sources rather than printless sources.
- ✓ Due to rapid development of ICT in electronic version, academic programme are wobbling in the connection between print and printless sources for user convenience.
- ✓ Today, the modern user is highly knowing the digital information through online as well as off line.

6. Factor Determination of Digital Learning:

6.1 Circumstance Pressure: In the academic library, the information has to fill up the user requirements as per academic curriculum. For several millennia, right up until just two decades ago, the library was just collect and store such as clay tablets, scrolls, printed books (Manguel, 2006). At the time the user had spent time 3 to 5 hours per day. Now it is very difficult to image the time spending much of more due to tolerance. Therefore, in the circumstance library has to modify the physical desktop to digital desktop through ICT for transforming the right information form hard to shift according to limited budget. The table narrates structure of seeking information.

6.2 Information Seeking by User:

All Category of Reader Expectations on Information	
Before Digitalization	After Digitalization
Catalogue	OPAC, Web-Catalogue
Reference	E-Collection-Database
Abstract & Index	Scanning, Printing, Reprogaphing
Translation	Abstract & Index-Hard & Soft
Atlas, Map	Internet & Intranet-open source

In the tabular academic libraries are convinced that digital text, now in its infancy, is likely to have a long future. Not only do they purchase electronic texts, but most academic libraries have also become publishers of electronic texts, whether they are digitizing large portions of their book holdings, or focusing on scanning a relatively small number of archival documents from their unique special collections. This shift to digital “holdings” has brought tremendous benefits to university researchers, students, and the general public.

6.3 Challenge & Risk into Digitations: The post-digital age, digital learning in education is the wholesome integration of modern telecommunications equipment and ICT resources, particularly the internet, into the education system (Tracy-1995). A digital learning capability is a cross functional proficiency in the process, practice and user relationship enable by digital media and infrastructure. A strong digital identity allows a library to be closed to its readers at anywhere. The Academic institution should be handled carefully before making digital source identifications where the source has to meet academic syllabus. This study suggests the following indications strategy for making best digital learning centre in academic libraries such are identification of behavior, technology training, selection of suitable ICT, monitoring antivirus updating, ensure copy right law, preservation & conservation, resource sharing and budget allocation.

6.4 Strengthen the Digital Learning: The transformation of library culture and practice by the adoption of information technology continues apace. An increasing quality of goods and service and a decreasing emphasis on the collection are the serious common factor in considering the transform the sources from academic libraries to buddy graduates. This study feels that libraries are not engaging in a broad range of novel activities based on

the oral observations of research scholar, working people in the industry. The following electronic technologies and services have incorporated into the everyday task of all professionalisms for providing the right information to right readers in a proper manner.

6.5 Electronic Environment: Not only are libraries seeking technological standards and presentation of resources in forms accessible to the broadest range of readers, but they are also lobbying to advance the public policy debate in ways that support broad access for the good of society as a whole.

6.6 Building Digital Collections: Building collections of digital resources that while not yet rivaling traditional collections in scope and bulk are substantial of high value and integrated in the traditional patterns of collection and use.

6.7 Webpage Design: Digital learning can be promoted in the form of distance learning of online course. The librarian should aware on webpage design and publish course materials with animation to easily understand by the user.

6.8 Set up Network: In academic institution libraries have to make a smooth relationship between other kinds of libraries effectively for providing materials via inter library loan to readers.

6.9 Digitalize Special Material: Such materials are rarely available which includes, in particular, out-of-copyright material, image collections, sheet music, maps, and other traditional library treasures. These can be delivered after digitizing in well and good condition.

6.10 Upgrading Resource, Software, Hardware and Skill: The up gradation process is very difficult one in library and it is impossible in the library sector for staff to acquire and practice skills and then use them for a lifetime; instead, they must learn and adapt, and there are real and substantial costs for supporting the necessary training and for paying a more highly talented person.

6.11 Measuring Sources: Finding new ways to measure the usage patterns and behaviors of readers, so as to anticipate and support their needs, bringing the right resources into play for readers. The digital environment facilitates such measurement and, accordingly, such feedback, giving a better allocation of resources than has ever been possible with print media.

6.12 Strengthening User Community: Librarians are more often than ever teachers on how to use electronic resources, and readers spend less time pursuing simple factual information at traditional reference desks.

6.13 E-Communication: The technical services of libraries are becoming increasingly business-like streamlined, and closely managed, with closer links than ever to vendors through electronic data interchange (EDI) and other forms of electronic interaction (Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp, Mail) that work to the advantage of all groups.

6.14 Generate Funding Sources: This kind of technical idea handling is a very dangerous one and may be given solution for making financial for smooth running the library process. Librarians are increasingly engaged in entrepreneurial efforts, whether solicited research and development funding from granting agencies, annual budget, fine amount, and reprography collection, Membership, developing partnerships with other entities in the library sector, or participating in cost-recovery projects in the commercial sector that serves and interacts with the library community.

6.15 Implication of Digital Tool: Physically, some stains disturb to human beings while using the digital learning continuously and lack of insufficient infrastructure facilities. This kind of problem will take away after implementing some technical tips to those who are using digital screen reading as follows;

- ✓ Avoid small font size and adjust the font as they like-above 40 age person (presbyopia problem).
- ✓ Provide subtitles for video or audio content is fundamental to the user experience.
- ✓ Recommending the touch interface using- over 80 age persons.
- ✓ Avoid small-screen devices (i.e. phones) for all.
- ✓ Don't rely on SMS to convey important information.
- ✓ Avoid splitting tasks across multiple screens if they require memory of previous actions.
- ✓ Prioritize shortcuts to previous choices ahead of new alternatives.
- ✓ Information designed as expert opinion may be more persuasive.
- ✓ Allow for greater time intervals in interactions (for example, server timeouts, and inactivity warnings).

7. Conclusion:

In the academic institution, teaching methodology has to be changed entirely and also framed syllabus pattern according to the later development of ICT. The computerized and digital type of education in which texts, audio or sound, pictures, images, graphics and video sources can be simultaneously presented online to library users. In conclusion, the institution should mount an intensive digital learning training program for staff as well as users adequately provide all the materials needed for digital learning application in curriculum implementation in higher education.

8. References:

1. <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6WNP-4SGD4S0-st> Mon day, 1995-2016.
2. Ollie cammbp, 2015, designing for the elderly: ways older people use digital technology differently, accessed on 27.1.2016.

3. <http://www.nap.edu/readbuedu.net>, accessed on Jan.23.2016.
4. Sabina nwana, challenges in the application of e-learning by secondary school teachers in Anambra state, Nigeria, pdf, accessed on jan.23.2016.
5. <http://abs.sagepub.com/content/45/3/436.short?rss=1&ssource=mfc>, accessed on Jan.29.2016.
6. <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0099133304001521>, accessed on Jan.29.2016.
7. Daniel Reed, 2014, Digital marketing solutions for way startup's needs.
8. Ashley Harshak,.et...al, ,2013,Building a digital culture.
9. Tina Barseghian, 2011, Three trends that online the future of teaching and technology.
10. Terje Hillesund, 2010, Digital reading spaces: How expert readers handle books, the Web and electronic paper, vol-15 - 4.
11. John D and Ctherine T, 2010, The future of thinking learning institutions in a digital age.
12. Walter J. Ong, 2008, Orality and literacy: The technologizing of the word, Routledge.
13. Akinola, C.I. 2005, The Challenges of reform, information and communication technology in business education, curriculum and information technology. Business Education Book of Readings, 3(5) 120p – 125.
14. Angela Weiler, 2005, Information-seeking behavior in generation Y students: Motivation, critical thinking, and learning theory, Journal of Academic Librarianship, vol. 31(1) 46p-53p.
15. Sundarajan, A, 2005, ICT and education: Challenges and practices. I4d: Information for Development. Retrieved from <http://www.i4donline.net/nov05/digitallearning.asp>.
16. Offorma G.C, 2002, Curriculum implementation and instruction: Onitsha: Uni-World Educational Publishers.